

THE CONCEPT OF MODERN APPROACH AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION AND ITS ESSENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10802733>

Abstract: This thesis discusses the modern approach to education and the concept of innovative technology and its essence. Opinions about the effectiveness of using innovative technologies are also presented.

Key words: Music education, methodology, innovative technology, subject.

Introduction.

Along with updating and improving the content of education and increasing the quality indicators, it is necessary to improve the qualifications of teachers-trainers, to keep them in step with the development of science and science, especially those who can effectively use information technologies and interactive methods, which are widely used in all fields. to prepare students who can freely communicate with the computer and to be able to apply it in their activities to ensure the effectiveness of the lesson, to create new educational positions together with interested ministries and agencies, and to train schoolchildren for professions measures are one of the important tasks of today.

The skillful use of multimedia tools for education is important in increasing the effectiveness of the teaching process. After all, in traditional education, students are taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, in accordance with the criteria of developmental education, students can learn, analyze, and draw conclusions by themselves. becomes important with its orientation. Therefore, the use of multimedia tools in the general secondary education system, their wide application in practice serves to increase the quality of education¹.

If we consider the approaches indicated in the scientific and literary sources on the problem of modern approaches and the use of innovative technologies in the educational process: S. N. Sazonova and T. V. Volosovets, the optimal performance of the educational institution, the mandatory development of the

¹ Альмяшева Л.В. Социализация молодежи посредством студенческих объединений // Вестник Челябинского государственного университета. - Челябинск. - 2013. – С. 141-143.

management of the target activities of all subjects, they believe that it ensures its formation and stabilization.

It is considered as a set of personal and professional qualities that ensure the effective implementation of competencies from professional and pedagogical approaches. Competency-based approach is one of the priorities of pedagogical thought, which has become increasingly popular in recent years.

The teacher's operational competence is determined by the set of skills necessary for professional activity: organizational, predictive, projective, scientific-methodological, expert, pedagogical improvisational skills.

Pedagogical experience shows that solving the problems of music education begins with the professional training of teachers. A teacher's pedagogical professional skills are impossible without effective and qualitative growth and timely acquisition of pedagogical competencies. Thus, such education, based not only on basic knowledge in a specific field, but also on general culture, including information culture, is relevant. In this regard, we can say that every teacher needs training in the field of modern innovative technologies.

In the process of music culture in general secondary schools, it is aimed at the development of students in various types of musical activities:

- ❖ musical literacy;
- ❖ listening to music;
- ❖ vocal performance;
- ❖ musical rhythmic movements;
- ❖ playing children's musical instruments.

Yu.M. Horvitz says that a person who knows technology and information skillfully and effectively has a different, new way of thinking, has a fundamentally different approach to assessing the problems that arise, organizing his work².

Today, informatization can be considered one of the main ways of modernizing the education system. Informatization related to education is an urgent and important issue in the modern world, and it is noted as one of the priority tasks of modern society. It ensures the active use of the ever-expanding intellectual potential of society, the integration of information technologies with the development of all spheres of life, and provides everyone in society with the opportunity to have reliable sources of information. Changes in society related to information processes help to create a qualitatively new information environment of society and accelerate scientific and technical progress, which

² Горвиц, Ю.М. Новые информационные технологии в дошкольном образовании. [Текст] / Ю.М. Горвиц, А.А. Чайнова, Н.Н. Подъяков — М.: ЛИНКА-ПРЕСС 1998. —328 с.

helps to develop the creative potential of an individual. The concept of information can be interpreted as information transmitted by people orally, in writing or in any other way. Currently, modern innovative information technologies are expanding and their fields of application are expanding.

Information technology is a process that uses a set of means and methods of data collection, processing and transmission to obtain new qualitative information about the state of an object, process or event (information product). Features of information technologies include active and effective use of society's information resources, help to optimize and automate information processes. At the current stage, information technology plays an important role in the implementation of the model of information interaction between people and in the process of preparing and distributing mass media. Information technology plays a key role in the development of the educational system and the intellectualization of society.

The main goal of introducing information technologies is to create a single information space of an educational institution, a system in which all participants of the educational process: administration, teachers, students and their parents participate and are connected at the information level. To do this, we need trained pedagogical personnel who can combine traditional teaching methods and modern information technologies. The interaction of modern information technologies with the field of education allows teachers to qualitatively change the content, methods and organizational forms of education. The main goal of these technologies in education is to develop the intellectual abilities of students in the information society, as well as to individualize, humanize and develop the educational process, and to improve the quality of education at all levels of the educational system.

Information and communication technology is a pedagogical technology that uses special software and technical tools to access various information sources (electronic, printed, instrumental, human) and means of joint activity aimed at achieving a certain result.

Subjects of communication technologies in the organization of general secondary education are those who directly implement it, that is, teachers. The objects of communicative technologies are aimed at direct communicative influence, that is, children of preschool age. The development of communication technologies has several stages:

- the first stage - theoretical, which ensures the formation of goals and tasks, the definition of the object;

- the second stage is methodological, it is related to planning, selection and justification of methods, methods and tools;

- the third stage is a procedural stage that ensures the practical implementation of the pedagogical project.

Scientist I. V. Robert, as modern information and communication technologies, software, hardware and technical tools, microprocessor and computer technologies, information transfer and offers an understanding of exchange systems.

Effective use of information and communication technologies for qualitative change of the educational process is one of the indicators of the development of society. In fact, the introduction of information and communication technologies in the form of the development of copyrighted multimedia projects, educational products, electronic music and game manuals into the practical activities of the music director increases the quality of the organization of the educational process and makes the process of the child's musical development more interesting and effective.

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